

COVAXIN(BBV152): HISTORY, COMPONENTS, MECHANISM, EFFICACY AND OTHER COVID-19 VACCINES***Sandhiya G.**

*M.Sc. Biotechnology, Department of Biotechnology, Vivekanandha Arts and Science College for Women, Salem, Tamil Nadu- 637303.

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Corresponding Author*Sandhiya G.**

M.Sc. Biotechnology, Department of Biotechnology, Vivekanandha Arts and Science College for Women, Salem, Tamil Nadu- 637303.

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ABSTRACT

SARS-CoV-2 is an RNA virus that rapidly spread across the world. It was first identified in Wuhan, in China. At that time, there were no specific drugs available to treat COVID-19. Health Care workers used some antiviral medicines and steroids to reduce the symptoms. Covaxin is made using a traditional method called the Whole Virion inactivated Vaccine which means the Virus is inactivated so it can't cause disease. But, still helps the body to learn to fight it [to boost the immune system]. It was developed by Bharat Biotech International Limited, located in Hyderabad, in partnership with National Institute of Virology (NIV) and Indian Council of Medical Research (ICMR). BBV152 is the code name of COVAXIN. It is India's first (indigenous) locally developed COVID-19 vaccine. It was developed using the NIV-2020-770 strain. BBV152 was combined with Algel-IMDG, where IMDG (Imidazoquinoline) improving vaccine's effectiveness. SARS-

CoV-2 is a round or slightly irregular virus with an outer envelope, it is tiny and measuring about 65-125 nm in diameter. One side has a curved in surface with a raised edge, this shape allows it to bind more strongly and make more contacts with ACE-2 receptor. During pandemic, Covaxin was allowed to be used in emergency situations, even though the full clinical trials happened. This special permission called Emergency Use Authorization (EUA). At that time, based on the early results (called interim analysis) from the clinical trials, the vaccine was found to be 81% effective. It is administered through the intramuscular route. The virus spreads mainly through the tiny droplets from coughing or sneezing When inhaled,

it enters the nose and begins to multiply. ACE-2 is the main receptor that allows COVID-19 to attach. These interact with T cells, which release cytokines that stimulate B cells to produce antibodies against SARS-CoV-2. It mainly targets the virus's spike protein. Covaxin represents a milestone in India's scientific and public health achievements, showcasing the potential of inactivated vaccines to deliver safe and effective protection during a global health crisis. Its development and deployment demonstrated India's capacity for rapid vaccine innovation, large-scale manufacturing, and efficient distribution, particularly in regions with limited resources.

KEYWORDS: COVID-19, inactivated, BBV152, indigenous, interim analysis, effective, antibodies.

INTRODUCTION

Covaxin is a COVID-19 vaccine made from a killed (inactivated) virus. It uses a special method called the "whole virion inactivated Vero cell" technology. It contains dead virus and boosts the immune system against infection.^[5] On March 11, 2020, WHO declared it a global pandemic.^[16] The World Health Organization named the illness "COVID-19", short for coronavirus disease 2019.^[15] SARS-CoV-2 mutations are a common outcome of viral replication seen worldwide. However, around 1.5 million children die each year from vaccine-preventable diseases because they were not given essential childhood vaccines.^[6] The spread of SARS-CoV-2 (the virus that causes COVID-19) caused serious problems around the world, including significant economic losses. The first COVID-19 case was found in Wuhan, China, at the seafood market, where live animals were being sold.^[10]

SARS-CoV-2 is an RNA virus of the Coronaviridae family that affects both animals and humans.^[1] Between December 19, 2019, and March 25, 2023, the virus rapidly spread across the globe, infecting around 761.4 million individuals and causing around 6.89 million deaths, with a death rate of 0.90%.^[3] Twenty-seven cases of pneumonia with an unknown cause were identified in Wuhan, Hubei province, China, on December 31, 2019. Wuhan, located in central China and has the population of about 11 million. The patients mainly presented with symptoms including dry cough, dyspnea, and fever.^[2] The World Health Organization officially named the clinical syndrome caused by SARS-CoV-2 COVID-19 on February 11, 2020. In humans, the lower respiratory tract is affected by this virus, causing in inflammatory pneumonia.^[1]

SARS-CoV-2 is the virus responsible for COVID-19. This virus emerged in 2019 and quickly spread to many parts of the world.^[5] Scientists sequenced SARS-CoV-2 and developed vaccines.^[5] According to reports from WHO, the B.1.617 strain of the coronavirus, which was first identified in India, has been classified as a variant of global concern. This variant is highly transmissible, may cause more severe disease, or reduce the effectiveness of public health measures.^[4] The appearance of variants of this virus has made the situation even more difficult to manage. Mutations can alter the virus behaviour.^[4] At that time, there were no specific drugs available to treat COVID-19. Doctors used some antiviral drugs and steroids to reduce lung inflammation and manage other symptoms.^[1]

Some drugs such as remdesivir, molnupiravir, and dexamethasone were tested to treat COVID-19. Immunotherapy drugs such as tocilizumab and baricitinib also showed benefits. These were evaluated in many clinical trials.^[10] As the most populous country with densely crowded cities, India faced significant challenges in its healthcare infrastructure, public health awareness, government funding, and socioeconomic stability.^[23] Real world studies from multiple countries increasingly demonstrate that widely available COVID-19 vaccines, such as BNT162b2 (Pfizer/BioNTech), mRNA-1273 (Moderna) and ChAdOx1 nCoV-19 (Oxford/AstraZeneca) are effective in preventing SARS-CoV-2 infection.^[38]

History of Vaccines and Covaxin

Edward Jenner used a cowpox virus to protect humans from smallpox. He chose it because the animal pox virus was more harmful in animals but caused only mild effects in humans. At the same time, it helped stimulate the immune system and provided protection against smallpox.^[7] Vaccination is the process used to protect people from childhood infections and has saved lives.^[8]

Covaxin is made using a traditional method called the whole virion inactivated vaccine technology. This means the virus is killed (inactivated) so it cannot cause disease, and still helps the body develop immunity against it.^[4] Attenuated and inactivated viral vaccines represent a traditional class of vaccines developed using well-established platforms. Attenuated vaccines use viruses weakened by repeated passage through cultured cells, so they cannot cause disease. This weakened form can still trigger an immune response without causing illness.^[8] For many years, inactivated vaccines have been effectively used to prevent viral diseases such as encephalitis, influenza, polio, and rabies. Similarly, BBV152 was developed using the same technology.^[5]

In India, the first wave of SARS-CoV-2 peaked in September 2020 and then slowly declined. In March 2021, new cases began to rise again. By December 17, 2021, there were about 272 million confirmed cases and over 5.3 million deaths worldwide. Around 8.3 billion vaccine doses had been given, according to WHO.^[1] Scientists, including Zhang Yong-Zhen's team at Fudan University, quickly worked to sequence the genome of the virus in early January 2020. They used a technique called metagenomic RNA sequencing, which helps find unknown viruses by analyzing genetic material from patient samples. The sample was taken from the lungs. Once they sequenced the virus, they uploaded it to the NCBI database so researchers around the world could begin working on tests, treatments, and vaccines.^[10]

Covaxin-induced antibodies were found to neutralize SARS-CoV-2 variants including B.1.1.7, B.1.1.28, B.1.351, and B.1.617. Vaccine effectiveness may vary depending on the individual and viral mutations.^[4] It was developed by Bharat Biotech International Limited, located in Hyderabad, in partnership with the National Institute of Virology (NIV) and the Indian Council of Medical Research (ICMR). BBV152 is the code name of Covaxin.^[11] It is India's first indigenous COVID-19 vaccine.^[12] In July 2020, ICMR stated that Covaxin should be given top priority and aimed to launch it by August 15, 2020, after completing all clinical trials and enrollment by July.^[12] In India, Bharat Biotech's vaccine (BBV152) was the second most widely administered during the pandemic, with 327 million doses given.^[9] A stable SARS-CoV-2 strain, called NIV-2020-770, which had a small change known as the Asp614Gly mutation, was used to develop Covaxin.^[9]

SARS-CoV-2 Structure

SARS-CoV-2 is a round or slightly irregular virus with an outer envelope. It is tiny, measuring about 65-125 nm in diameter. They possess an envelope and contain a single-stranded, positive sense RNA genome ranging from 26 kb to 32 in size. The spike(S) protein sticks out like a crown and helps new virus particles form (Figure 1). The envelope(E) protein is important for infection and virus replication. Together, S, E and M make the virus's RNA and is key for making new viruses.^[15,25] One side has a curved in surface with a raised edge. This shape allows it to bind more strongly and make more contacts with ACE-2.^[27]

The coronavirus spike protein has three main components: a large ectodomain, a single-pass transmembrane anchor, and a short intracellular tail. The ectodomain is divided into two subunits: S1, responsible for receptor binding, and S2, which mediates membrane fusion. Electron microscopy studies show that the spike protein forms a clove-shaped trimer,

consisting of three S1 heads and a trimeric S2 stalk. During viral entry, the S1 subunit attaches to host cell receptors, while the S2 subunit fuses the viral and host membranes, enabling the viral genome to enter the cell. These processes receptor binding and membrane fusion are essential early steps in coronavirus infection and key targets.^[42]

Figure 1: Structure of coronavirus.

Covaxin components

BBV152(Covaxin) is a whole Virus inactivated Vaccine developed using the NIV-2020-770 strain.^[13] Vaccine platforms are mainly of two types: those based on viral components and those based on the whole virus. Viral Components include protein subunits, virus-like particles, DNA and RNA vaccines, ad viral vectors (replicating and non-replicating). Whole-virus vaccines include inactivated and live-attenuated vaccines.^[29] BBV152 was combined with Algel or Algel-IMDG, where IMDG (Imidazoquinoline) boosts immunity by promoting a strong Th 1 response, improving vaccine's effectiveness. IMDG was also used in flu vaccines to enhance cell mediated immunity. Tests in mice, rats, and rabbits showed their antibodies could neutralize the whole virus.^[13] The vaccine includes beta-propiolactone, a chemical that kill the virus by breaking its genetic material but still allow the immune system to recognize and fight it.^[9] The vaccine remains stable and effective when stored between 2°C and 8°C.^[5] It also contains an ingredient called Alhydroxiquim II, which boosts the body's immune response and makes the vaccine more effective.^[4] It has an extra ingredient called Adjuvants, like TLR 7/8 agonist and aluminium hydroxide, which helps the body create a stronger immune response.^[5] Vero CCL-81 cells were grown using a special nutrient liquid (DMEM with 5-10% calf serum). The virus containing liquid was then cleaned using column chromatography and made more concentrated using filtration system.^[9]

Clinical Development

A vaccine must undergo clinical trials and demonstrate safety and effectiveness before being administered to large populations.^[33] Phase 1 trials test the vaccine's safety and immune response in fewer than 100 healthy people.^[18] Phase 2 trials tested the BBV152 inactivated COVID-19 vaccine for safety and immune response in healthy volunteers (aged 12-65) at nine hospitals across India. Screening included SARS-CoV-2 PCR and antibody tests at a central lab. People who tested positive in either screening test were not included. The gap between screening and vaccination was about 3 days. Those over 65, pregnant or breastfeeding women, and people with other health conditions were also excluded.^[20] Phase 2 trials involved over 100 participants in different groups to confirm safety, measure immune response, and find the right dose.^[18] It was approved for Phase 1 and Phase 2 trials by the Drugs Controller General of India and testing began in July 2020 at multiple institutes.^[12]

Phase 3 (about 32 months) tests thousands of people to assess efficacy. Low disease prevalence during Phase 3 required a larger participant pool.^[18] The trial was approved by India's Drug Authority and hospital ethics committees, and followed International Good Clinical Practice guidelines.^[20] After all trials, regulatory bodies review the vaccine and approve it if deemed safe and effective. Post-release monitoring tracks side effects and effectiveness.^[18] It has been observed that 552 participants received the first dose of either Covaxin or Covishield. After excluding 37 cases, 515 individuals who completed both doses were included in the final analysis. The average age was about 45 years, with nearly 59% males and 41% females. Most participants (85%) were under 60, while 15% were above 60. About one-fourth had comorbidities like diabetes, hypertension or heart disease, but none had cancer, chronic kidney disease, or type 1 diabetes.^[26]

Interim Analysis

On 16th January 2021, the Covaxin vaccine was allowed to be used in emergency situations, even though the full clinical trials were happened at that time. This special permission called Emergency Use Authorization (EUA).^[4] At that time, based on the early results (called interim analysis) from the clinical trials, the vaccine was found to be 81% effective. This means able to protect 81 out of every 100 people from getting COVID-19 during the trial.^[4] In animal laboratory studies, D614G mutation is possessed by SARS-CoV-2 variant. This vaccine gets finally WHO Authorization approval, after successfully completed phase 3 COVAXIN efficacy rate was 77.8% for symptomatic COVID-19.^[14] Animal studies for

WHO approved COVID-19 vaccines used several SARS-CoV-2 models, including mice with human ACE2, adapted mice, hamsters and non-human primates.^[19] Following Interim results from its Phase III trial, Covaxin received approval for use in India, and to date, more than 340 million doses have been administered.^[41]

Vaccine administration and Efficacy

Covaxin is an inactivated virus-based vaccine designed to protect against SARS-CoV-2. It is administered through the intramuscular route. It is considered as India's indigenous inactivated COVID-19 Vaccine.^[5] The choice of vaccine was upto each person, not random. For Covaxin recipients, samples were taken on Day 0 (before the first dose) and Day 28 (before the second dose).^[22] Live attenuated virus vaccines contain a weakened form of the virus that can multiply enough in a healthy person to trigger a strong immune response. Inactivated vaccines use killed or modified pathogens that cannot replicate, but they usually produce a weaker or shorter-lasting immune response compared to live attenuated vaccines. Protein subunit vaccines are made using parts of the virus.^[17] The vaccine was given as a 0.5 ml of intramuscular injection in the upper arm. Each vial held a single ready to use dose. No Preventive medicines were given before or after vaccination.^[20]

Table 1: Major SARS-CoV-2 variants, Their Lineages, and Geographic Origin.

Coronaviridae				
Variant	Alpha	Beta	Gamma	Iota
Lineage	B.1.1.7	B.1.351	P.1	B.1.526
Geographical Origin	First found in UK	First found in South Africa	First found in California	First found in New York

Healthcare systems worldwide were not prepared to handle the sudden, large-scale challenges caused by the COVID-19 pandemic.^[21] Injection site effects after a deltoid vaccine shot are mostly mild and temporary, serious ones are uncommon and usually reported by the person, not the trial doctors.^[35] Vaccines Effectiveness varied based on disease severity, symptoms and the type of virus variant. For the Alpha variant, vaccines provided strong protection against infection, symptoms and severe illness.^[14] Bharat Biotech reports Covaxin's efficacy as 63% for asymptomatic infections, 78% for mild to severe symptomatic cases, 65% effectiveness against the Delta Variant, 93% protection against severe COVID-19 outcomes. It can prevent the Coronavirus from replicating and boosts the immune system to fight against it.^[5]

So many people around the world got infected with COVID-19, the virus had more chances to change (mutate). These changes caused new variants to develop like (Table 1) Alpha Variant (B.1.1.7) – first found in the UK, Beta variant (B.1.351) – first found in South Africa, Gamma variant (P.1) – first found in California, SA, Iota variant (B.1.526) – first found in New York, USA.^[9] With the Beta and Delta Variants, Vaccines offered less protection against symptoms, but they still helped reduced the severity of the disease. Among the five main variants of concern, Omicron was the most widely spread, while the other variants accounted for less than 1% of cases.^[14] In India's Phase 3 trial, BBV152 was 77.8% effective against symptoms and gave 65.2% protection against the Delta Variant.^[15] In the phase ½ trial, Covaxin was given as a 0.5 ml intramuscular dose on day 1 and day 14. The trial was approved and received emergency use authorization from DCGI (Drug Controller General of India). An ICMR study later reported that Covaxin works better against the Delta Plus Variant, while Covishield is more effective against the Delta Variant.^[24]

Treatments

At that time, there were no specific drugs available to treat COVID-19. Doctors used some antiviral medicines other symptoms.^[1] Fever is treated with antipyretics like paracetamol and dry cough with expectorants such as Guaifenesin. Severe cases with respiratory distress or hypoxemia require immediate Oxygen at 5L/min to maintain SpO₂ ≥90% in adults/children and 92-95% in pregnant women.^[2] Some medicines like remdesivir, molnupiravir and dexamethasone were tested to treat COVID-19. Immunotherapy drugs like tocilizumab and baricitinib also showed benefits. These were tried in many clinical trials. But since some resistance was seen vaccines become the main cool to fight COVID-19 during the pandemic.^[10]

Mechanism of SARS-CoV-2 Infection

The beta coronavirus, which enters the body through the ACE2 receptor, was first identified in Wuhan, Hubei Province, China.^[16] Angiotensin-converting enzyme 2 (ACE2) binds strongly with the N-terminal helix of ACE2, giving the virus higher binding affinity. The virus spreads mainly through tiny droplets from coughing or sneezing. When inhaled, virus enters the nose and begins to replicate. ACE2 is the main receptor that allows SARS-CoV-2 to attach.^[27] The viral spike protein binds to ACE2 and enables viral entry.^[27] It disrupts normal pathways and elevates angiotensin II levels, which can trigger cytokine storms and severe respiratory distress.^[31] An enzyme called furin, present in human cells but not in

SARS-CoV, helps the virus enter more easily. After entry, the virus multiplies in the nose with little early immune response, allowing detection nasal swabs.^[27]

Later, it moves to the respiratory tract, where a stronger immune reaction occurs. At this stage, symptoms appear, and cytokines from the immune system may influence how severe the disease becomes. In beta and lambda variants, infected epithelial cells are the main viral source.^[27] ACE2 control blood pressure by converting angiotensin II (which narrows blood vessels). It is found in many cells, especially on the surfaces of the nose and lungs, making it easier for the virus to infect the respiratory system. It is also present in other parts of the body, such as blood vessels, heart, stomach, and kidneys.^[1]

Mechanism and Immune Response of Covaxin

Covaxin is an inactivated vaccine that stimulate B-cell activation. B cells interact with T cells, whose cytokines drive antibody production against SARS-CoV-2.^[24] It reduces disease severity but does not fully prevent infection.^[5] Adjuvants enhance vaccine response but may trigger autoimmune or inflammatory reactions in genetically susceptible individuals.^[28] It neutralizes the Alpha variant, which was first detected in December 2020. It also showed effectiveness against the Beta and Delta variants, it mainly targets the virus's spike protein. Even though the virus in the vaccine is dead and can't cause infection, it still helps the body learn to fight the real virus by creating an immune response.^[5] Phase I/II studies of Covaxin showed strong humoral and cell-mediated immune responses. Although CD4+ and CD8+ T cell activity was seen only in some participants in Phase I, Phase II demonstrated a significant improvement in cell-mediated immunity. Covaxin also enhanced T cell memory, as indicated by increased CD4+, CD45RO+, and CD27+ T cells, supporting antigen recall responses.^[1]

Its adjuvant, a TLR7/8 agonist, promotes Th1 immunity while suppressing Th2 responses, which is beneficial for COVID-19 vaccines. This adjuvant may also strengthen CD8+ T cell activity.^[1] During a natural SARS-CoV-2 infection, the body develops innate and adaptive immune responses to fight the virus. However, how long this protection lasts are still unclear. COVID-19 vaccines work differently by introducing viral antigens, which triggers a specific immune response and create immune memory with continued vaccination, this can also help achieve herd immunity in the population.^[39] It is still unclear how well COVID-19 vaccines make neutralizing antibodies, how strong their antibodies are, and how long they last.^[40] Once inside, it replicates and spreads to nearby cells, triggering pyroptosis and releasing damage-associated molecular patterns (DAMPs).^[16]

These DAMPs are detected by pattern recognition receptors (PRRs), such as Toll-like receptors (TLR3, TLR7, TLR8, TLR9) and viral RNA sensors (MDA-5, RIG-I), leading to the production of type I interferons (IFN- α , IFN- β), which provide antiviral protection. This response activates the NLRP3 gene and promotes cellular events like calcium influx, ROS production, and protein aggregation, resulting in the formation of NLRP3 inflammasomes.^[16] These inflammasomes trigger caspase-1 activation, cleavage of pro-inflammatory cytokines (IL-1 β , IL-18), and gasdermin-D-mediated pyroptosis, linking NLRP3 activity to COVID-19 severity. Elevated lactate dehydrogenase (LDH) levels, a marker of pyroptosis, have been found in severely ill patients. Although SARS-CoV-2 shows sensitivity to type I interferons further studies are needed to understand how different genes regulate this response.^[16]

Some Other Vaccines For SARS-CoV-2

During the pandemic, several vaccines were approved for use in people, such as Moderna and Pfizer-BioNTech, Covishield (Oxford-AstraZeneca), Sputnik V (Gamaleya), Vero cell (Sinopharm), CoronaVac (Sinovac), and Covaxin (Bharat Biotech). These vaccines were developed to combat COVID-19 and administered worldwide.^[23,24] A recombinant COVID-19 vaccine contains only a specific viral antigen, reducing the risk of side effects seen with live or attenuated vaccines, while demonstrating enhanced safety and effectiveness.^[29]

Covishield, produced by the Serum Institute of India, is a monovalent vaccine formulated using a non-replicating chimpanzee adenovirus vector. This vector is engineered to deliver the genetic sequence encoding the spike (S) glycoprotein of SARS-CoV-2. After administration, the spike glycoprotein stimulates local immune activity, leading to the generation of neutralizing antibodies and the activation of a cellular immune response.^[28] It was a collaboration between Oxford University and AstraZeneca.^[31] It is widely administered in India and shows an efficacy of around 80%.^[30] Several Regulatory Authorities have authorised the Oxford-AstraZeneca COVID-19 vaccine for disease prevention.^[32] The Pfizer-BioNTech Comirnaty vaccine, created in partnership by Pfizer and BioNTech, represents a well-known example of an mRNA-based vaccine.^[31]

The Sinovac-CoronaVac vaccine, produced by Sinovac Research and Development Co., Ltd. serves as a representative example of inactivated virus vaccines.^[31] This vaccine has achieved broad coverage, and significant focus has been placed on evaluating potential adverse events.^[33] It is formulated with aluminium hydroxide adjuvant. It is produced using African

green Monkey Kidney (Vero) cells inoculated with the SARS-CoV-2 CNO2 strain. The primary vaccination schedule consists of two doses administered 2 to 4 weeks apart.^[34]

Sputnik V or Gam-COVID-Vac, is a COVID-19 vaccine developed by the Gamaleya National Centre of Epidemiology and Microbiology in Russia. It employs a two-dose adenoviral vector platform to induce a strong immune response by generating antibodies against the SARS-CoV-2 Spike (S) protein.^[36] Following National Healthcare guidelines, clinical staff administered 0.5 ml doses of Sputnik V into the deltoid muscle. The first dose used rAd26 and the second rAd5, given 21 days apart, each containing around 1×10^{11} adenoviral particles encoding the spike protein.^[37]

CONCLUSION

Covaxin, India's first Indigenous inactivated COVID-19 vaccine, has proven to be safe and effective in trials as well as routine vaccination programs. Administered as a two-dose regimen, it effectively stimulates the immune system to produce protective antibodies against SARS-CoV-2, reducing the risk of infection, severe illness, and hospitalization. Offers a broad immune response by exposing the body to multiple viral antigens, not just the spike protein. Its development showcased rapid regulatory approvals and successful large-scale clinical trials in India. With over 340 million doses administered in India, Covaxin has played a critical role in the nation's vaccination efforts. Incorporating booster doses, improving vaccine accessibility, and strengthening surveillance systems will further enhance protection levels. Lessons from Covaxin's development can guide rapid vaccine design and manufacturing for future outbreaks. Investment in research, manufacturing, and distribution infrastructure is crucial for global health security. The vaccine's development also highlighted the effectiveness of strong public-private partnerships, swift regulatory approvals, and rigorous large-scale clinical trials. Continuous monitoring of its effectiveness, particularly against emerging variants, along with booster doses, will be essential to sustain long-term protection and support broader public health strategies. Moving forward, continuous genomic surveillance, post-marketing safety studies, and booster dose strategies will be essential to sustain its protective efficacy. Covaxin's journey serves as a blueprint for strengthening global vaccine self-reliance, accelerating pandemic response strategies, and building international confidence in vaccines developed in emerging economies.

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